

Annex to: Scientific opinion on the microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen and defrosting of frozen ungulates meat. doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2026.9825

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Annex C – pH values in meat from different ungulate species

A total of 59 references (see Table C.1) reporting post-mortem pH data were compiled across various animal species. Only studies (or groups of animals/carcasses within them) that considered conditions leading to expected normal pH decline and pH_u were included (i.e. studies/groups considering e.g. stressed animals, electro-stimulated carcasses, etc., were excluded). The number of studies available per species is as follows: Bovine (20 studies), Caprine (8), Ovine (14), Porcine (8), Equine (5), Deer and wild boar (2 each).

Table C.1. Reported pH values in meat from different ungulate species at different points of stabilisation period and after the stabilisation period.

Animal species	Condition	Time (post-mortem)	pH	Reference
Bovine	Conventional slaughter with stunning	3.00, 6.00, 24.00	5.95, 5.84, 5.72	Barrasso et al., 2022
Bovine	-	0.00, 1.00, 2.00, 3.00, 4.00, 5.00, 6.00, 7.00, 8.00, 9.00, 10.00, 11.00, 12.00, 13.00, 14.00, 15.00, 16.00, 17.00, 18.00, 19.00, 20.00, 21.00, 22.00, 23.00, 24.00	7.00, 6.60, 6.33, 6.15, 6.03, 5.95, 5.89, 5.86, 5.83, 5.82, 5.80, 5.80, 5.79, 5.79, 5.78, 5.78, 5.78, 5.78, 5.78, 5.78, 5.78, 5.78, 5.78, 5.78	Cadavez et al., 2019
Bovine	-	24.00	5.95	Cardoso et al., 2013
Bovine	-	1.00, 7.00, 17.00, 25.00, 31.00	6.93, 6.52, 5.84, 5.98, 5.73	Crowley et al., 2009
Bovine	-	24.00	5.62	Gudjónsdóttir et al., 2015
Bovine	High glycogen level	0.58, 0.58, 4.94, 7.56, 23.72	6.65, 6.43, 5.78, 5.61, 5.42	Hamoen et al., 2013
Bovine	Light carcasses	0.44, 0.73, 4.36, 6.11, 7.85, 24.29	6.35, 6.16, 5.77, 5.74, 5.72, 5.58	Hamoen et al., 2013
Bovine	Non electrostimulated carcasses	0.19, 0.38, 8.09, 5.89, 24.31	6.80, 6.56, 5.95, 5.82, 5.37	Hamoen et al., 2013
Bovine	M. longissimus dorsi	4.25, 8.04, 10.24, 7.42, 7.33, 6.59, 9.09	6.16, 5.97, 5.84, 6.17, 5.52, 5.63, 5.95	Hannula and Puolanne, 2004
Bovine	M. semimembranosus	5.56, 6.21, 8.51, 7.27, 7.10, 6.13, 9.41	5.84, 5.79, 5.86, 6.05, 5.46, 5.68, 5.74	Hannula and Puolanne, 2004
Bovine	Buffaloe (M. biceps femoris)	0.00, 2.00, 4.00, 6.00, 8.00, 10.00, 12.00, 14.00, 16.00,	6.44, 6.36, 6.18, 6.07, 5.99, 5.90, 5.77, 5.65, 5.55,	Jorge et al., 2006

Animal species	Condition	Time (post-mortem)	pH	Reference
		18.00, 20.00, 22.00, 24.00	5.49, 5.42, 5.37, 5.26	
Bovine	Buffaloe (M. longissimus dorsi)	0.00, 2.00, 4.00, 6.00, 8.00, 10.00, 12.00, 14.00, 16.00, 18.00, 20.00, 22.00, 24.00	6.43, 6.31, 6.03, 5.94, 5.86, 5.78, 5.69, 5.58, 5.50, 5.47, 5.45, 5.39, 5.32	Jorge et al., 2006
Bovine	-	24.00	5.55	Kahraman and Gurbuz, 2019
Bovine	Hot bonned inner (M. biceps femoris)	1.00, 3.00, 5.00, 48.00	6.53, 6.24, 6.10, 5.43	Kuffi et al., 2018
Bovine	Hot bonned outer (M. biceps femoris)	1.00, 3.00, 5.00, 48.00	6.88, 6.66, 6.28, 5.45	Kuffi et al., 2018
Bovine	Intact inner (M. biceps femoris)	1.00, 3.00, 5.00, 48.00	6.61, 5.72, 5.40, 5.45	Kuffi et al., 2018
Bovine	Intact outer (M. biceps femoris)	1.00, 3.00, 5.00, 48.00	6.92, 6.81, 6.57, 5.32	Kuffi et al., 2018
Bovine	Fast pH decline group	0.50, 2.00, 6.00, 12.00, 24.00, 48.00, 72.00	6.62, 6.37, 5.92, 5.61, 5.48, 5.44, 5.47	Ma et al., 2022
Bovine	Slow pH decline group	0.50, 2.00, 6.00, 12.00, 24.00, 48.00, 72.00	6.89, 6.71, 6.36, 5.85, 5.61, 5.48, 5.53	Ma et al., 2022
Bovine	M. longissimus dorsi	24.00	5.67	Mach et al., 2008
Bovine	M. longissimus dorsi (3 replicates)	1.44, 3.00, 5.06, 8.04, 12.02, 18.08, 24.11, 1.55, 2.99, 4.96, 8.03, 12.15, 18.08, 24.19, 1.46, 3.08, 6.09, 10.07, 12.07, 24.02	7.36, 6.16, 5.71, 5.60, 5.51, 5.49, 5.49, 7.05, 6.00, 5.65, 5.50, 5.38, 5.41, 5.40, 7.01, 6.10, 5.67, 5.58, 5.56, 5.51	Mallikarjunan and Mittal 1994
Bovine	-	0.00, 24.00	7.00, 5.60	McSharry et al., 2021a
Bovine	Delayed chilling	0.77, 1.49, 3.03, 5.98, 8.99, 11.96, 23.94	6.81, 6.55, 6.24, 5.73, 5.56, 5.46, 5.41	Mohrhauser et al., 2014
Bovine	Normal chilling	0.76, 1.53, 2.94, 5.99, 8.99, 12.01, 23.94	6.75, 6.63, 6.15, 6.02, 5.74, 5.66, 5.50	Mohrhauser et al., 2014
Bovine	-	1.00, 24.00, 48.00	6.95, 6.17, 5.62	Reid et al., 2017
Bovine	Forequarter	72.00	5.99	Stella et al., 2022
Bovine	Hindquarter	72.00	5.87	Stella et al., 2022
Bovine	-	48.00	5.46	Stenström et al., 2014
Bovine	-	0.75, 3.00, 6.00, 12.00, 24.00	6.80, 6.65, 6.40, 6.33, 5.85	Zhang et al., 2018
Bovine	-	24.00	5.76	Mendes et al., 2024
Caprine	-	0.50, 24.00	6.30, 5.50	Assis et al., 2015
Caprine	-	0.00, 1.00, 3.00, 6.00, 12.00, 24.00	6.70, 6.48, 6.33, 6.20, 6.04, 5.89	Hussain et al., 2021
Caprine	M. longissimus dorsi	24.00	5.96	Kannan et al., 2001

Animal species	Condition	Time (post-mortem)	pH	Reference
Caprine	M. semimembranosus	24.00	6.07	Kannan et al., 2001
Caprine	M. triceps brachii	24.00	6.33	Kannan et al., 2001
Caprine	Old animals (unstressed)	0.25, 24.00	6.80, 5.70	Kannan et al., 2003
Caprine	Young animals (unstressed)	0.25, 24.00	6.80, 6.10	Kannan et al., 2003
Caprine	-	1.00, 24.00	6.60, 6.00	Ortega et al., 2016
Caprine	-	1.00, 24.00	6.50, 5.80	Santos et al., 2008
Caprine	-	0.75, 24.00	5.88, 5.48	Sen et al., 2004
Caprine	-	0.00, 24.00	6.60, 5.80	Teixeira et al., 2017
Deer (farmed and slaughtered)	M. supraspinatus	4.00, 24.00	6.08, 5.68	Bykowska et al., 2019
Deer (farmed and slaughtered)	M. longissimus	4.00, 24.00	5.85, 5.51	Bykowska et al., 2019
Deer (farmed and slaughtered)	M. semimembranosus	4.00, 24.00	5.93, 5.58	Bykowska et al., 2019
Deer (farmed and slaughtered)	M. longissimus thoracis et lumborum (pasture fed)	9.00, 24.00, 48.00	5.35, 5.47, 5.60	Volpelli et al., 2003
Deer (farmed and slaughtered)	M. longissimus thoracis et lumborum (concentrate fed)	9.00, 24.00, 48.00	5.37, 5.50, 5.61	Volpelli et al., 2003
Deer (farmed and slaughtered)	M. semimembranosus (pasture fed)	0.75, 9.00, 24.00, 48.00	6.48, 5.48, 5.53, 5.63	Volpelli et al., 2003
Deer (farmed and slaughtered)	M. semimembranosus (concentrate fed)	0.75, 9.00, 24.00, 48.00	6.39, 5.40, 5.53, 5.62	Volpelli et al., 2003
Equine	M. longissimus lumborum	0.75, 24.00, 48.00	6.79, 5.72, 5.67	Litwinczuk et al., 2008
Equine	M. semitendinosus	0.75, 24.00, 48.00	6.73, 5.69, 5.68	Litwinczuk et al., 2008
Equine	-	24.00	5.56	Gomez and Lorenzo, 2012
Equine	-	24.00	5.46	Lorenzo and Gomez, 2012
Equine	Males	0.50, 1.00, 24.00, 48.00	6.88, 6.54, 5.59, 5.72	Tateo et al., 2008
Equine	Females	0.50, 1.00, 24.00, 48.00	6.92, 6.49, 5.63, 5.68	Tateo et al., 2008
Equine	-	48.00	5.60	Beldarrain et al., 2021

Animal species	Condition	Time (post-mortem)	pH	Reference
Ovine		24.00	5.85	Aguayo-Ulloa et al., 2022
Ovine	-	1.00, 3.00, 6.00, 24.00	6.54, 6.47, 6.44, 6.19	Cetin et al., 2012
Ovine	-	24.00	5.58	Constantino et al., 2012
Ovine	-	0.75, 24.00	6.53, 5.75	Držaić et al., 2016
Ovine	Conventional chilling	0.00, 0.50, 2.00, 5.00, 24.00	6.67, 6.59, 6.37, 6.23, 5.90	Fernandez and Vieira, 2012
Ovine	Conventional chilling	0.00, 0.75, 3.00, 5.00, 24.00	6.70, 6.61, 6.43, 6.23, 5.81	Vieira and Fernandez, 2014
Ovine	-	0.00, 1.00, 3.00, 6.00, 12.00, 24.00	6.72, 6.54, 6.35, 6.16, 5.99, 5.85	Hussain et al., 2021
Ovine	-	0.75, 1.00, 3.00, 6.00, 24.00	6.54, 6.35, 6.16, 5.99, 5.85	Mickelson et al., 2025
Ovine	-	1.00, 24.00	6.71, 5.85	Ortega et al., 2016
Ovine	-	1.00, 24.00	6.60, 5.60	Santos et al., 2008
Ovine	-	~24.00	5.75	Sañudo et al., 2012
Ovine	-	0.75, 24.00	5.93, 5.46	Sen et al., 2004
Ovine	-	0.00, 24.00	6.70, 5.50	Teixeira et al., 2017
Ovine	-	24.00	5.70	Velarde et al., 2003
Porcine	-	24.00	5.70	Choi et al., 2024
Porcine	-	0.75, 0.75, 24.00, 24.00	5.93, 6.09, 5.62, 5.82*	Čobanović et al., 2020
Porcine	-	0.75, 24.00	6.20, 5.50	Guo et al., 2021
Porcine	-	0.00, 0.25, 0.50, 1.00, 2.00, 3.00, 6.00, 12.00, 24.00	7.22, 7.00, 6.70, 6.50, 6.19, 6.00, 5.86, 5.67, 5.61	Lonergan, 2012
Porcine	-	0.25, 0.75, 1.00, 3.00, 6.00, 9.00, 12.00, 24.00	6.86, 6.56, 6.39, 6.04, 5.83, 5.78, 5.71, 5.79	Moreira et al., 2022
Porcine	-	0.25, 0.75, 1.00, 3.00, 6.00, 9.00, 12.00, 24.00	6.99, 6.77, 6.56, 6.18, 6.04, 5.88, 5.79, 5.84	Moreira et al., 2022
Porcine	-	24.00	5.88	Najar-Villarreal et al., 2020
Porcine	-	1.05, 1.03, 1.38, 1.65, 1.94, 2.22, 2.52, 2.74, 2.92, 3.12, 3.42, 3.68, 4.08, 4.43, 4.83, 5.35, 5.98, 5.97, 5.48, 4.71, 4.24, 3.74, 3.32, 2.89, 2.32, 1.80, 1.38, 24.00, 24.00	6.37, 6.52, 6.26, 6.18, 6.10, 6.05, 6.00, 5.95, 5.92, 5.89, 5.84, 5.80, 5.77, 5.72, 5.68, 5.65, 5.62, 6.06, 6.08, 6.08, 6.11, 6.13, 6.18, 6.23, 6.29, 6.36, 6.45, 6.07, 5.61	Scheffler and Gerrard, 2007
Porcine	-	0.75, 24.00	6.13, 5.51	Scheier and Schmidt, 2013
Wild boar (farmed and slaughtered)	M. longissimus dorsi	0.75, 24.00	6.33, 5.80	Kasprzyk et al., 2010

Animal species	Condition	Time (post-mortem)	pH	Reference
Wild boar (farmed and slaughtered)	M. semimembranosus	0.75, 24.00	6.54, 5.85	Kasprzyk et al., 2010
Wild boar (farmed and slaughtered)	M. longissimus dorsi	1.00, 2.00, 6.00, 12.00, 24.00, 48.00	6.18, 5.97, 5.75, 5.64, 5.57, 5.46	Marchiori and de Felicio, 2003
Wild boar (farmed and slaughtered)	M. semimembranosus	1.00, 2.00, 6.00, 12.00, 24.00, 48.00	6.22, 6.00, 5.78, 5.68, 5.60, 5.47	Marchiori and de Felicio, 2003

* minimum and maximum values reported for the two time points

Figures C.1, C.2 and C.3 show the post-mortem pH decline profiles considered within Baseline I conditions (mean) and Baseline II conditions (conservative), obtained based on the data reported within [Table C.1](#).

Figure C.1. Post-mortem pH decline profile for bovine meat. Parameters for Baseline I conditions (mean): $k=0.34$, $pH_{min}=5.71$. Parameters for Baseline II conditions (conservative): $k=0.34$, $pH_{min} = 6.18 (\mu+2s)$.

Figure C.2. Post-mortem pH decline profile for porcine meat. Parameters for Baseline I conditions (mean): $k=0.44$, $pH_{min}=5.7$. Parameters for Baseline II conditions (conservative): $k=0.44$, $pH_{min} = 5.99$ ($\mu+2s$).

Figure C.3. Post-mortem pH decline profile for ovine meat. Parameters for Baseline I conditions (mean): $k=0.27$, $pH_{min}=5.76$. Parameters for Baseline II conditions (conservative): $k=0.27$, $pH_{min} = 6.14$ ($\mu+2s$).

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